
HISTOPATHOLOGICAL EFFECT OF CRUDE OIL
FRACTIONS ON THE SKIN OF *Heterobranchus bidorsalis* JUVENILES

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ABSTRACT

The histopathological effect of crude oil fractions on the skin of *Heterobranchus bidorsalis* (mean weight, $14.02 \pm 0.36\text{g}$) juveniles was studied. The exposure of the fish to 0.50, 1.00, 2.00, 4.00, 8.00 mL^{-1} Bonny-light crude oil (BLCO), premium motor spirit (PMS), dual purpose kerosene (DPK), lubricating engine oil (LEO) and a control (0.00mL^{-1}) indicated significant increases ($P < 0.05$; $P < 0.01$) in the isoelectric points (IEP) of the skins of the fish with increasing oil concentrations. The exposure of the fish to BLCO elicited higher IEP values than when exposed to PMS, DPK, LEO and the control. The decline in IEP values at day 14 (40%), day 28 (60%) and day 42 (72%) of the study period reflected the magnitude of recovery of the fish skins from oil exposures, showing the extent of relief the epidermal and dermal cells of the skins had undergone from the exposure to crude oil compounds. Microscopic observation revealed some structural abnormalities among the epidermal/dermal cells. It was concluded that some fish species can store aromatic petroleum hydrocarbons derived from polluted waters and pass such compounds to higher trophic levels hence the need for improved environmental management.

KEYWORDS: anthropogenic activities, aquatic environment, fingerlings, pollutants.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing emphasis on improving the quality of aquatic ecosystems and monitoring surface waters has highlighted the need to know what factors cause environmental deterioration (Krahn *et al.*, 1992). Pollution of water sources from crude oil and petroleum products may play a major role in the decline of aquatic animals and biodiversity. The concentration of these pollutants at 0.10mL^{-1} , accelerated the death of many fish fingerlings although the reduction in their survival times was less than 20% (Lee, 1975). Some deviations occur with *Heterobranchus* species when crude oil is used as a pollutant, but generally, zooplankton and fingerlings are sensitive to oil concentrations of between 0.00 and 0.10mL^{-1} . In fact, fingerlings will die after the first 24 hours (Mironov, 1969).

Increasing awareness of the adverse effects of anthropogenic activities and pollution on aquatic environment has focused interest on health of fish populations and possibilities of utilizing these health parameters to assess the quality of an aquatic environment (Henry *et al.*, 2004).

The survival of fish depends mainly on the way the oil is introduced into the aquatic environment. When oil products are emulsified in seawater, the damage is much greater than when oil films are found on the surface. Apart from being toxic, the mechanical action of tiny oil droplets on the gill apparatus is important. The survival of fish in relatively high concentrations of oil on the first day of exposure does not indicate that they resist oil pollution (Tatem *et al.*, 1979). It has been suggested that the uptake and translocation of crude oil compounds in fish may be through the gills, the gut or the intestinal walls (Roubal *et al.*, 1977).

Some deleterious effects on fish species as a result of crude oil exposures have been identified (Neff and Anderson, 1987). These effects include: alteration of the immune response mechanisms, changes in liver metabolism, haemorrhage and even death. There is dearth of published information in Nigeria and many other developing countries on the histopathological effects of exposing fish to crude oil concentrations. Therefore, this study was designed to investigate the magnitude of damage on the skin of *Heterobranchus*

bidorsalis juveniles when exposed to various concentrations of crude oil and its fractions. Histopathological studies of the effect of crude oil compounds on the skin of the fish were carried out and the implications of the results obtained discussed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study involved four samples of crude oil and its fractions namely: Bonny-light crude oil (BLCO), premium motor spirit (PMS), Kerosene (DPK), and lubricating engine oil (LEO). A control experiment, without oil contamination, was used to compare the responses of the fish to various concentrations of the oil pollutants. Hence, the experiment was based on a 4 x 6 Completely Randomized Block Design (CRBD), with 24 experimental treatments.

One thousand, four hundred and forty (1440) juveniles of *H. bidorsalis* (Geoffroy St. Hilaire, 1809) {mean weight \pm standard error of mean (s.e.m), $14.02 \pm 0.36g$ } were purchased from Akia Agro-Allied Production Fish Farm in Igbide, Delta State, Nigeria and transported to the Fisheries Laboratory of Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki. The fish specimens were conveyed in five plastic containers (25 litre capacity). The water temperature ($27 \pm 0.80^{\circ}C$) was maintained with ice cubes held in a portable cooler. At the fisheries laboratory in Abakaliki, the fishes were acclimated for 14 days and fed a 38% crude protein maintenance diet at 3% body weight per day ($bw.d^{-1}$).

At the commencement of the study, 60 plastic containers (25l) were filled with dechlorinated tap water to the 24 litre mark and contaminated with 5ml each of the four oil samples (BLCO, PMS, DPK and LEO) with concentrations: 0.50, 1.00, 2.00, 4.00 and $8.00ml^{-1}$. Twelve (12) plastic containers used as controls were also filled with water (24l) and left uncontaminated with oil samples. Each of the 72 plastic containers was subsequently stocked at random with 20 fish per container.

The toxicity period lasted for 4 days (96 hours) while the recovery period (42 days) was monitored at fortnightly intervals. At the end of the toxicity period the surviving fish and plastic containers were washed with clean tap water before the recovery period commenced. An already formulated 38% crude protein diet (Table 1) was then fed to the fish at 3% $bw.d^{-1}$ during the recovery period. Skin samples of the fish were obtained during each study period for histopathological studies. Records of fish mortality and survivals were taken. The water temperature ($26 \pm 0.82^{\circ}C$) and pH (6.62 ± 0.2) were recorded with the aid of a Celsius maximum and minimum thermometer and a pH meter (Model Ph-1-201-L) respectively.

Skin tissues of fish from each triplicate treatment of BLCO, PMS, DPK, LEO and the control were dissected with the aid of sharp surgical blades and scissors and washed in distilled water to remove traces of blood. The clean skin tissues were then preserved in 100% ethanol placed in clean microphage tubes. The preserved skin tissues were later taken to the Histopathology Department of National Orthopedic Hospital, Enugu where histological analyses of the skin specimens were carried out.

Skin samples were prepared into slides at the hospital by cutting into sections of 5 microns. This was followed by drying and staining using the routine histomaline methods. In this case, staining was done through the use of Harrison's haemosine; while differentiation was by the application of 1% acid/alcohol. The skin sections were subsequently blued in tap scorch water and counterstained in 1% oesine for 3 minutes. The sections were finally dehydrated in alcohol and mounted in DPX on clean transparent plastic slides. Histopathological study of the epidermal and dermal cells of the skin was carried out by observation of the slides under a high-powered microscope. Structural abnormalities of the skin cells were noted and ranked as isoelectric points of the health conditions of the cells, vis-à-vis the fish. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze the data for statistical significance ($P < 0.05$).

RESULTS

Table 1 show the proximate compositions of the diet fed to *H. bidorsalis* juveniles during the study. Table 2 shows the isoelectric points on the skin of the fish exposed to different concentrations of BLCO, PMS, DPK, LEO and the control during the toxicity and recovery periods. Table 3 shows the percentage

mortality and survival of the fish. The control fish recorded lower values of isoelectric points (IEP) on their skins than those exposed to the various oil concentrations (Table 2). IEP values of the skin cells increased as the concentrations of BLCO, PMS, DPK and LEO increased from 0.50 to 8.00 mL⁻¹. This trend was prevalent both at the toxicity and recovery periods of the study (Table 2). The exposure of the fishes to BLCO concentration gave higher values of IEP than when exposed to either PMS, DPK, LEO or the control (Table 2).

Among the oil types, IEP values of the fish showed a decreasing trend in the following order: BLCO > PMS > DPK > LEO. This trend was expressed in the fishes irrespective of the oil concentrations applied. Significantly, IEP values of the skin cells were reduced by 40% at day 14, 60% at day 28 and 72% at day 42. The range values of the IEP values of the skins of the control fish was between 0.40 ± 0.01 and 0.44 ± 0.01p1 and were not significantly different (P > 0.05) and were virtually of the same magnitude. In addition, the IEP values at day 42 for 0.50m/L⁻¹ DPK (0.45 ± 0.01 p1) and 1.00m/L⁻¹ LEO (0.44 ± 0.02 p1) nearly approximated the corresponding IEP values of the controls i.e. 0.42 ± 0.01p1 and 0.43 ± 0.02p1 respectively. Statistical analyses of the results from this study indicated that the IEP values of the skin cells varied significantly as the fishes were exposed to the various oil concentrations (P < 0.05; P < 0.01) (Table 2).

The state of the epidermal and dermal cells of the skins of the fish determined the histopathological rankings of isoelectric points (IEP) during the study. Microscopic observation of these cells revealed some deviations in the expected staining pattern of the nuclei and cytoplasm. The degree at which the nuclei were stained to blue/black and the cytoplasm to pink was adopted in isoelectric points as the magnitude of structural abnormalities that had occurred to the epidermal/dermal cells due to oil exposures. It was observed that the fish skin cells showed losses in the ability of their nuclei/cytoplasm to be stained as the oil concentrations increased from 0.50 to 8.00m/L⁻¹.

The percent mortality (PM) and survival (PS) of the fish both at the toxicity and the recovery periods (Table 3), indicated that the fish subjected to 4.00m/L⁻¹ and 8.00m/L⁻¹ concentrations of the various oil types died more and survived less. Obviously, the control fish showed zero mortality which was equivalent to 100% survival, throughout the study period (Table 3). Among the oil types, however, it was apparent that the fishes tolerated waters contaminated with PMS than with BLCO, DPK or LEO. This was exemplified by the comparatively lower mortality rate with fish treated with PMS (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

Histopathological study of the skin of *H. bidorsalis* juveniles in this research showed some structural abnormalities in the appearance of the nuclei and cytoplasm of the epidermal and dermal cells after staining. The distortions in staining ability might be due to the exposure of the fishes to different concentrations of crude oil and its fractions. The degrees of the deviation of the nuclei/cytoplasm of the skin cells from the expected staining pattern were reflected on the intensity of the blue/black coloration of the nuclei, on one hand, and of pink coloration of the cytoplasm on the other.

These intensities were ranked as isoelectric points (IEP) of the skins exposed to various concentrations of oil. In some occasions, the skins showed a progressive loss in their ability to be stained, indicating probably the presence of oedema (ie. the skins becoming tough to cut). This result is consistent with the report of Oladimeju and Onwumere (1988) which stated *inter alia* that the skins of *H. bidorsalis* are damaged by effluents from petroleum oil refineries in Nigeria.

From this study, the exposure of *H. bidorsalis* juveniles to BLCO (0.50 – 8.00m/L⁻¹) affected the histopathological conditions of the skin more than when the fishes were exposed to PMS, DPK and LEO. This assertion is supported by the relatively higher IEP values recorded with BLCO than with those recorded with either PMS, DPK or LEO. The decreasing trend in the IEP values of the fish skins: as exemplified by BLCO > PMS > DPK > LEO, implies that the histopathological conditions of the skins of

H. bidorsalis juveniles could be affected in the same decreasing pattern when exposed to waters contaminated with two or more of the above oil pollutants.

The estimated percent reductions in the IEP values of the skin as the fishes recuperated from the oil exposures on day 14 (40%), day 28 (60%) and day 42 (72%) reflected the extent of recovery the epidermal and dermal cells had undergone as the days progressed. It was obvious that IEP values of the skin decreased tremendously between day 14 and day 42 and this cut across the various oil concentrations to which the fishes were previously exposed. However, the closeness between the IEP values of fishes exposed to 0.50m/L^{-1} DPK and 1.00m/L^{-1} LEO and those of their controls was obvious at day 42. This implies that the recovery of the fish skins from their exposures to the DPK and LEO concentrations was nearly complete since their IEP values approximated those of the controls. Comparatively, IEP values of fish skins higher than the IEP values of the control fish on the same day 42 implies that the fish specimens in question might not have fully recovered from their exposures to oil pollutants. The results of this study agree with the report of Khan *et al.* (1995) who stated that minnows retain absorbed petroleum hydrocarbon 14 days after their transfer to uncontaminated seawater. Similarly, Kennicutt and Sweet (1992) reported that Spill-related contamination was detected in intertidal limpet (*Nacella concinna*) two years after the release of crude oil into the Author Harbour in the Antarctic Peninsula. It is evident from these studies that man is confronted with a debilitating problem since oil spills occur regularly into aquatic systems and fishes in such systems are inadvertently consumed. Lee (1975) reported that some fish species can store aromatic petroleum hydrocarbons derived from polluted waters and pass such compounds to higher trophic levels.

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Table 1: Proximate Composition of Experimental Diet.

Nutrient (%)	% Composition
Crude protein	37.58
Ether extract	5.18
Ash	10.48
Dry matter	11.80
Nitrogen free extract	34.46
Total	100.00

Table 2: Isoelectric Points (pI) on the Skin of *H. bidorsalis* Juveniles Exposed to Different Concentrations of Crude Oil and Crude Oil Fractions.

Study period	Duration (Days)	Crude Oil and fractions	Oil Concentration (mL ⁻¹)						Overall mean
			0.50	1.00	2.00	4.00	8.00	Control 0.00	
Toxicity period	4	BLCO ¹	8.06 ^a ± 0.04	9.95 ^b ± 0.05	12.05 ^c ± 0.06	14.83 ^d ± 0.11	17.19 ^e ± 0.13	0.41 ^f ± 0.01	10.39 ± 0.16
		PMS ²	7.87 ^a ± 0.02	9.36 ^b ± 0.04	11.22 ^c ± 0.07	14.12 ^d ± 0.12	16.33 ^e ± 0.12	0.42 ^f ± 0.02	9.89 ± 0.15
		DPK ³	6.65 ^a ± 0.03	8.03 ^b ± 0.03	10.21 ^c ± 0.05	12.06 ^d ± 0.13	13.80 ^e ± 0.14	0.44 ^f ± 0.01	8.53 ± 0.13
		LEO ⁴	4.76 ± 0.01	6.62 ± 0.02	8.53 ± 0.07	11.45 ± 0.09	13.25 ± 0.11	0.43 ± 0.02	7.57 ± 0.08
Recovery Period	14	BLCO	4.73 ^a ± 0.02	5.97 ^b ± 0.04	7.23 ^c ± 0.06	8.95 ^d ± 0.04	10.31 ^e ± 0.12	0.40 ^f ± 0.03	6.27 ± 0.06
		PMS	4.72 ^a ± 0.01	5.62 ^b ± 0.04	6.74 ^c ± 0.04	8.48 ^d ± 0.06	9.80 ^e ± 0.10	0.40 ^f ± 0.02	5.96 ± 0.03
		DPK	3.99 ^a ± 0.03	4.82 ^b ± 0.02	6.13 ^c ± 0.03	7.23 ^d ± 0.04	8.28 ^e ± 0.09	0.42 ^f ± 0.01	5.14 ± 0.04
		LEO	2.85 ± 0.02	3.97 ^b ± 0.02	5.12 ^c ± 0.03	6.97 ^d ± 0.03	7.95 ^e ± 0.04	0.41 ^f ± 0.02	4.53 ± 0.02
	28	BLCO	1.89 ^a ± 0.01	2.39 ^b ± 0.03	2.89 ^c ± 0.01	3.58 ^d ± 0.02	4.12 ± 0.03	0.43 ^f ± 0.02	2.55 ± 0.02
		PMS	1.89 ^a ± 0.02	2.25 ^b ± 0.02	2.70 ^b ± 0.02	3.39 ^c ± 0.01	3.92 ^c ± 0.02	0.42 ^d ± 0.03	2.42 ± 0.03
		DPK	1.60 ^a ± 0.03	1.93 ^a ± 0.03	2.45 ^c ± 0.01	2.89 ^d ± 0.01	5.65 ^e ± 0.05	0.42 ^f ± 0.01	2.10 ± 0.02
		LEO	1.44 ^a ± 0.02	1.22 ^a ± 0.04	2.05 ^b ± 0.02	2.75 ^b ± 0.03	3.20 ^c ± 0.03	0.40 ^d ± 0.01	1.85 ± 0.03
	42	BLCO	0.53 ^a ± 0.01	0.67 ^b ± 0.02	0.81 ^c ± 0.02	1.00 ^d ± 0.01	1.16 ^d ± 0.02	0.42 ^e ± 0.01	0.77 ± 0.02
		PMS	0.53 ^a ± 0.02	0.63 ^b ± 0.01	0.75 ^c ± 0.01	0.95 ^d ± 0.02	1.10 ^e ± 0.01	0.41 ^f ± 0.02	0.73 ± 0.01
		DPK	0.45 ^a ± 0.01	0.54 ^b ± 0.01	0.69 ^c ± 0.02	0.81 ^d ± 0.04	0.93 ^e ± 0.01	0.42 ^a ± 0.01	0.64 ± 0.02
		LEO	0.32 ^a ± 0.01	0.44 ^b ± 0.02	0.57 ^c ± 0.01	0.77 ^d ± 0.03	0.90 ^e ± 0.02	0.43 ^b ± 0.02	0.57 ± 0.02

(1) Bony-light crude oil, (2) Premium motor spirit, (3) kerosene, (4) lubricating engine oil. Numbers in the same row but with different superscripts differ significantly (P < 0.05; P < 0.01).

Table 3: Mortality and Survival of *H. bidorsalis* Juveniles Exposed to Different Concentrations of Crude Oil and Crude Oil Fractions.

Study period	Duration (Days)	Crude Oil and fractions	% Mortality						% Survival					
			Concentration of Crude Oil and its Fractions (mL ⁻¹)					Control	Concentration of Crude Oil and its Fractions (mL ⁻¹)					Control
			0.50	1.00	2.00	4.00	8.00		0.50	1.00	2.00	4.00	8.00	
Toxicity period	4	BLCO ¹	2.00	5.00	5.00	40.00	50.00	0.00	98.00	95.00	60.00	60.00	50.00	100.00
		PMS ²	1.00	2.00	2.00	20.00	30.00	0.00	99.00	98.00	80.00	80.00	70.00	100.00
		DPK ³	1.00	3.00	4.00	40.00	50.00	0.00	99.00	97.00	60.00	60.00	50.00	100.00
		LEO ⁴	2.00	2.00	10.00	50.00	70.00	0.00	98.00	98.00	90.00	50.00	30.00	100.00
Recovery Period	14	BLCO	2.00	3.00	4.00	32.00	40.00	0.00	98.00	97.00	96.00	68.00	60.00	100.00
		PMS	1.00	1.00	1.00	16.00	24.00	0.00	99.00	99.00	99.00	84.00	76.00	100.00
		DPK	1.00	2.00	2.00	32.00	40.00	0.00	99.00	98.00	98.00	68.00	60.00	100.00
		LEO	1.00	1.00	6.00	40.00	52.00	0.00	99.00	99.00	94.00	60.00	48.00	100.00
	28	BLCO	1.00	2.00	2.00	24.00	36.00	0.00	99.00	98.00	98.00	76.00	64.00	100.00
		PMS	0.00	0.00	1.00	12.00	18.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	99.00	88.00	82.00	100.00
		DPK	0.00	1.00	1.00	24.00	32.00	0.00	100.00	99.00	99.00	76.00	68.00	100.00
		LEO	0.00	1.00	3.00	33.00	42.00	0.00	100.00	99.00	97.00	67.00	58.00	100.00
	42	BLCO	0.00	1.00	1.00	16.00	26.00	0.00	100.00	99.00	99.00	84.00	74.00	100.00
		PMS	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.00	14.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	94.00	86.00	100.00
		DPK	0.00	0.00	0.00	16.00	30.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	84.00	70.00	100.00
		LEO	0.00	0.00	0.00	24.00	40.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	76.00	60.00	100.00

(1)Bony-light crude oil, (2) Premium motor spirit, (3) kerosene, (4) lubricating engine oil.

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